

Supplementary Material C

Details on Meta-Analytic Results

C1. Forest Plot for all Included Effect Sizes and Study Quality Ratings

Author(s) and year	Hedge's g [95% CI]	Study DIAD rating			
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.69 [-1.22, -0.16]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.90 [-1.44, -0.36]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-1.47 [-2.05, -0.89]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-1.63 [-2.22, -1.03]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.12 [-0.40, 0.63]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.00 [-0.51, 0.51]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.11 [-0.41, 0.62]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.31 [-0.82, 0.21]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.24 [-0.28, 0.76]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.35 [-0.17, 0.87]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.12 [-0.64, 0.39]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.50 [-0.03, 1.02]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	1.20 [0.64, 1.76]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.44 [-0.08, 0.96]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.17 [-0.68, 0.35]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.66 [-1.19, -0.13]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	1.09 [0.54, 1.64]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.40 [-0.12, 0.91]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.26 [-0.78, 0.25]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.81 [0.28, 1.35]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.10 [-0.41, 0.62]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.61 [-1.14, -0.08]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-2.15 [-2.79, -1.50]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.83 [-1.37, -0.29]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-1.47 [-2.05, -0.89]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-2.15 [-2.79, -1.50]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.51 [-1.03, 0.01]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.61 [0.08, 1.13]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.18 [-0.34, 0.69]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.18 [-0.34, 0.69]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.30 [-0.22, 0.82]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.23 [-0.75, 0.28]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.23 [-0.75, 0.28]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.65 [0.12, 1.17]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	1.07 [0.52, 1.62]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.33 [-0.19, 0.85]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.43 [-0.09, 0.95]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	-0.35 [-0.87, 0.17]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.88 [0.34, 1.42]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.47 [-0.05, 0.99]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.07 [-0.44, 0.59]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.73 [0.20, 1.26]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.33 [-0.18, 0.85]	++	++	-	+
Ling & van Schaik (2002)	0.03 [-0.48, 0.55]	++	++	-	+
Miller (2011)	0.55 [0.05, 1.04]	++	++	-	---
Moshagen, Musch & Göritz (2009)	-0.06 [-0.40, 0.28]	++	++	-	++
Moshagen, Musch & Göritz (2009)	0.09 [-0.26, 0.45]	++	++	-	++
Moshagen, Musch & Göritz (2009)	0.44 [0.09, 0.78]	++	++	-	++
Moshagen, Musch & Göritz (2009)	-0.30 [-0.65, 0.06]	++	++	-	++
Perrig, Ueffing, Opwis & Brühlmann (2023)	0.06 [-0.17, 0.29]	++	++	-	++
Perrig, Ueffing, Opwis & Brühlmann (2023)	0.22 [-0.02, 0.45]	++	++	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.52 [0.08, 0.96]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.52 [0.08, 0.96]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.78 [0.33, 1.23]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.78 [0.33, 1.23]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.60 [0.15, 1.04]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.60 [0.15, 1.04]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.48 [0.04, 0.92]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.48 [0.04, 0.92]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.70 [0.25, 1.14]	-	+	-	++
Reinecke & Bernstein (2011)	0.70 [0.25, 1.14]	-	+	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	0.21 [-0.43, 0.85]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	-0.11 [-0.75, 0.52]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	0.40 [-0.23, 1.02]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	0.03 [-0.59, 0.65]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	0.40 [-0.23, 1.02]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	0.03 [-0.59, 0.65]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	0.22 [-0.42, 0.86]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	-0.04 [-0.68, 0.59]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	0.30 [-0.26, 0.86]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2015)	-0.13 [-0.69, 0.42]	-	++	-	---
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.80 [0.35, 1.26]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.60 [0.16, 1.05]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.74 [0.29, 1.20]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.05 [-0.39, 0.49]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.31 [-0.14, 0.75]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.19 [-0.25, 0.63]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.11 [-0.32, 0.55]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.20 [-0.24, 0.64]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.15 [-0.29, 0.59]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.05 [-0.39, 0.49]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.91 [0.34, 1.48]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.29 [-0.26, 0.83]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	1.09 [0.51, 1.68]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.27 [-0.28, 0.81]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.49 [-0.06, 1.04]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.12 [-0.43, 0.66]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.50 [-0.05, 1.05]	++	++	-	++
Reppa & McDougall (2022)	0.22 [-0.33, 0.76]	++	++	-	++

Note. Forest plot of the correlated and hierarchical effects (CHE) model, applying a constant sampling correlation of .50 and robust variance estimation (RVE). Effect sizes are reported in

the corrected standardized mean difference Hedge's g . Positive values indicate better performance with an aesthetically *pleasing* interface, while negative values indicate worse performance (i.e., better performance with an aesthetically *unpleasing* interface). Each effect size's mean is represented by a black square with whiskers showing the 95% confidence interval (CI). The size of each square reflects the precision of the corresponding estimate. The overall effect is represented by a diamond, with its center indicating the pooled estimate and its width showing the CI limits (Viechtbauer, 2024c). The four columns to the right of the forest plot display the Study Design and Implementation Assessment Device (Study DIAD) ratings for each effect and include: (Q1) construct validity or "fit between concept and operations," (Q2) internal validity or "clarity of causal inference," (Q3) external validity or "generality of findings," and (Q4) statistical conclusion validity or "precision of outcome estimation" (Valentine & Cooper, 2008, p. 140). The illustration of the Study DIAD ratings was adapted from Pfeiffer et al. (2024). Note that the Study DIAD ratings are the same across effect sizes from the same study.

C2. Associations Between Moderator Variables Indicated by Cramer's *V* Values

Moderator Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	
1 Reporting of device	–																		
2 Interface type	.60	–																	
3 Aesthetic measurement	.57	.68	–																
4 Time of aesthetic measurement	.29	.53	.38	–															
5 Presentation of interface during aesthetic measurement	.36	.40	.70	.29	–														
6 Color manipulation	.16	.73	.56	.52	.36	–													
7 Texture manipulation	.19	.51	.03	.63	.01	.21	–												
8 Layout manipulation	.01	.67	.05	.59	.11	.11	.41	–											
9 Typography manipulation	.49	.59	.29	.49	.13	.31	.39	.45	–										
10 Graphics manipulation	.28	.52	.16	.56	.13	.28	.64	.32	.71	–									
11 Complexity manipulation	.17	.70	.28	.46	.23	.76	.25	.31	.26	.29	–								
12 Difference between aesthetic conditions	.21	.35	.53	.29	.47	.29	.12	.24	.19	.20	.27	–							
13 Type of task	.06	.55	.29	.24	.43	.33	.50	.42	.34	.59	.27	.35	–						
14 Actual usage context	.75	.57	.52	.24	.48	.23	.21	.18	.36	.12	.27	.41	.22	–					
15 Intended usage context	.02	.54	.58	.47	.41	.54	.21	.08	.13	.26	.41	.23	.32	.28	–				
16 Mismatch of contexts	.17	.49	.27	.20	.35	.07	.07	.29	.03	.27	.23	.47	.31	.47	.62	–			
17 Performance measurement	.08	.41	.37	.34	.13	.40	.34	.39	.40	.50	.46	.23	.37	.17	.29	.19	–		
18 Control of confounders	.31	.51	.54	.30	.72	.55	.36	.61	.47	.51	.38	.18	.40	.38	.32	.25	.30	–	

Note. Reported values reflect associations between moderators based on their final coding, which may differ from the original coding scheme (see section 2.5.1 in the main text) due to category merging based on study availability. The number of aesthetic manipulations was excluded as a moderator due to multicollinearity ($V > .80$) with graphics manipulation and typography manipulation. Similarly, shape manipulation was excluded

due to multicollinearity ($V > .80$) with interface type. Further, interaction time, reference point for aesthetic measurement, and level of inherent usability were omitted from the analysis, as only a single category remained after filtering based on the minimum number of primary studies ($k \geq 4$).